

FOCCUS

Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean
for Copernicus users

D2.2: 1st version of data or development

WP2: New insight of high-resolution coastal observations

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1. Executive summary

The **FOCCUS project** (<https://foccus-project.eu/>) aims to enhance coastal ocean observation and forecasting for Copernicus users by designing and implementing a range of high-resolution data products. The **work package 2 (WP)** focuses on improving pan-European **innovative coastal ocean observations** in response to society and EU policy needs in the context of climate change.

The **data products** of innovative coastal observations, described in the Deliverable 2.1 - Data Report [M12] will be integrated in coastal modelling and coastal applications work packages to address pressing environmental and societal challenges (ESC).

This **Deliverable 2.2**, provides the first version of the data products within the WP2/3, that are provided in various formats, including NetCDF (.nc), Comma-separated values (.csv), and shapefile (.shp), as seen in the [Table 1](#). Coastal and river data inventories (not included in Table 1), providing detailed information, will be available in Deliverable D2.3, scheduled for release on June 30th, 2025. All data products will be validated in the project's second phase (starting in M18), with some of them containing very preliminary results. Final data products will be submitted in **M32**. Datasets that are listed in [Table 1](#), that still have in the current version a restricted access, will be made available to the FOCCUS project partners by request.

The datasets have been uploaded to the [Zenodo Community of FOCCUS](#). Zenodo was chosen due to its **long-term preservation** capabilities, clear **versioning** system, generous **storage** allowance (50 GB is available by default, more on demand), and built-in **usage tracking**. The platform's ability to **assign DOIs to each publication** enhances data discoverability and citability. Furthermore, integration with the existing FOCCUS project community folder facilitates organization and collaboration. [Annex I](#) provides a step-by-step guide to uploading datasets to the Zenodo repository.

2. Access to data products

[Table 1](#) summarises the **list of data products** being designed in the context of the WP2 that will be used in downstream WPs of coastal models (WP 6/7) and coastal applications (WP 8/9). Each data product has the link to the data access /last column).

Table 1.- High-resolution coastal observations data products, including the data access link.

#	Task	Data product	Lead	Coverage (area of interest)	Format	Data version	Data access link (DOI)
1.	2.1.1	Sea level	CLS	European seas (Mediterranean, Black Sea, Atlantic up to 66°N, Baltic)	netCDF	v0.1	FOCCUS dataset S6A 20Hz L3 NRT: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14882808 Non FOCCUS datasets¹: - Copernicus Marine Service dataset: S6A 5Hz L3 NRT: https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00147 SWOT Nadir L3 5HZ: https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00147 - CNES dataset: SWOT swath L3 2km (v2.0) https://doi.org/10.24400/527896/A01-2023.017 SWOT swath L3 250m (v1.0.2) https://doi.org/10.24400/527896/A01-2024.003
2.	2.1.1	Sea surface temperature	CNR	North Adriatic Sea	netCDF	v0.1	High-Resolution Merged Multi-Sensor (L3S) SST over the North Adriatic Sea: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14726911
3.	2.1.1	Sea ice changes	NERSC	Arctic Ocean (Svalbard, Greenland coastal zone)	netCDF	v0.1	Level-2 Fast Sea Ice Detection https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14773094
4.	2.1.2	HR total surface currents	NERSC	Norwegian coastal zone	netCDF	v0.1	High-Resolution Total Surface Currents: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14646111
5.	2.1.3	BGC anomalies & trends	CNR	North Adriatic Sea	netCDF	v0.1	Biogeochemical weekly means and anomalies from S3-OLCI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14866192 Biogeochemical trends from S3-OLCI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14753957
6.	2.1.3	Seagrass and macroalgae maps	BC	German Bight, Western Mediterranean (Balearic Sea)	netCDF	v0.1	Emerged seagrass and macroalgae in the German Bight: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14724926 ; Submerged Aquatic Vegetation at the Balearic Islands: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14701760

¹ FOCCUS did not fund these related datasets and may have different metadata standards, but they are potentially useful for coastal models and applications within the FOCCUS project.

7.	2.1.4	Beach monitoring products	SOCIB	Western Mediterranean (Balearic Sea); Black Sea (NW); Atlantic Ocean (Lisbon coastal zone)	netCDF and shapefile	v0.3 v0.2 V1 v0.2 v0.4	High-resolution coastal topobathymetries: https://zenodo.org/records/14735676 Wave parameters (in situ): https://zenodo.org/records/14735397 Total Water Level: https://zenodo.org/records/14766519 Shoreline position: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14810942 Midia and Mangalia Sea level radar level sensor data (2022): https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14724295
8.	2.2.1	Ocean currents	CLS	Mediterranean Sea (western)	netCDF	v0.1	Total surface currents in the Western Mediterranean Sea from Deep learning https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14826522
9.	2.2.1	HABs probability maps	NERSC	Norwegian coastal zone	netCDF	v0.1	Probability detection of harmful algae https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14748521
10.	2.2.1	Inland-marine water connectivity	CNR	Adriatic Sea coastal zone (Po River Delta)	csv	v0.1	Riverine Inherent Optical Properties https://zenodo.org/records/14836288
11.	2.2.2	Sea level and currents	NERSC	Atlantic: NW European Shelf; Atlantic; Nordic Seas, Norwegian coast	netCDF	v0.1	Sea-level, currents and water properties induced by eddies https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14825347
12.	2.2.2	FRM for OC and SST radiometer obs	CNR	Adriatic Sea coastal zone (Po River Delta) North Sea	Csv netCDF		In-situ radiometry in riverine waters https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14853170 In-situ FRM SST from ISAR https://zenodo.org/records/1490637410.5281/zenodo.14906373
13.	2.3.1	Beach morphodynamic processes	SOCIB	Western Mediterranean (Balearic Sea) Black Sea (NW); Atlantic Ocean (Lisbon coastal zone); Southern North Sea	netCDF	v1 V0.1 v0.1	Satellite Derived Bathymetry https://zenodo.org/records/14734739 Beach-imaging derived beach wracks https://zenodo.org/uploads/14808058 Shoreline position (same as 2.1.4) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14810942
14.	2.13	BGC anomalies and trends	BC	Black Sea, North Sea, Iberian Coast	netCDF	v0.1	Black Sea: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14883807

Annex I: Steps to upload the datasets in Zenodo

This annex provides a **step-by-step guide to uploading datasets to the Zenodo** repository, ensuring data accessibility, proper citation, and long-term preservation.

- **Create a Zenodo Account:**
 - Go to zenodo.org and click 'Log in' or 'Sign in'
 - You can sign up using existing credentials (GitHub, ORCID, etc.) or create a new account with your email address.
- **Select the FOCCUS project** under '[select a community](#)'

- **Upload your dataset**
 - Click the '[New upload](#)' call-to-action button.
 - Drag and drop your dataset files into the upload area or click 'upload files' to browse and select them.

- Zenodo supports various file formats (including NetCDF, CSV, SHP).
- **Fill in the metadata:** provide the essential information of your dataset, including:
 - Create DOI if not already available
 - Resource type* = Dataset (by default)
 - Title* = Title of data product (as in D2.1 -Data Report, section 3)
 - Publication date* (if previously published, use the original publication date)
 - Creators* (author/s with ORCID IDs, if available)
 - Description (including relevant context, methodology, and usage notes).
 - For the initial release (v0.1) of the data products, include a brief description as in D2.1 - Data Report, section 3
 - For the final version of the data products, include a comprehensive description following the format below to ensure consistency and the inclusion of important details that are only available in the file metadata”
 - Training dataset (header 1)
 - Brief explanation of the dataset including its purpose, contents (amount of images) and other relevant information, i.e. in what context the training data set is used.
 - Technical details (header 1)
 - The next sections contain relevant information lacking elsewhere in the input forms.
 - Data preprocessing (header 2)
 - Details about any preprocessing steps applied to the data, such as for example augmentation.
 - Data splitting (header 2)
 - How is the training dataset split into training, validation and prediction.
 - Classes, labels and annotations (header 2)
 - Describe the classes and labels used. If images are annotated, describe the type (bounding boxes, segmentation masks).
 - Parameters (header 2)
 - Include parameters from the training dataset. It is recommended here to include links to [vocabularies](#).
 - Data sources (header 2)
 - Instrument/gear, sensors, website, database, conditions under which images were captured.
 - Data quality (header 2)
 - Information on data quality and reliability, including any known limitations or sources of error.
 - Image resolution (header 2)
 - Dimensions of images in pixels (width x height)
 - Spatial coverage (header 2)
 - Spatial coverage: geographic extent covered by the data
 - Contact information (header 2)
 - Who to contact for questions about the training dataset or the application related to it.

- Licenses = CC-BY-4.0 or other appropriate open license., as in D2.1 - Data Report, section 3)
- Contributors (can include persons, or organizations, same options as for creators)
- Keywords and subjects (as in D2.1 - Data Report, Annex I)
- Languages = English (by default)
- Dates = Multiple dates can be added with different types: Accepted, available, collected, copyrighted, created, issued, other, submitted, updated, valid, withdrawn.
- Version =
 - V 0.1 (first draft, i.e. not yet ready for use and implementation). Subsequent drafts will increase by "0.1".
 - V 1.0: (first final version). Subsequent final revisions will increase by "0.1". Subsequent finals will increase by "1.0" above the version being revised.
- Publisher = Zenodo (by default)
- Funding = FOCCUS (to be selected from the drop-down list). Add Funder = European Commission (BE)
- Alternate identifiers, if any.
- Related works and publications or projects (link to any relevant articles or websites)
- References = (as in D2.1 - Data Report, section 4)
- Software: can include links to software applied on the training dataset.
- **Set the visibility** (by default) and publish:
 - Public (to be selected by default): Anyone can access and download the dataset.
 - Restricted: Access is limited to FOCCUS project partners (access by request).
 - Embargoed: The dataset will be published publicly after a specified date.
- **Publish the dataset**
 - Once you have reviewed all the information and set the visibility, click "Publish."
 - Zenodo will assign a DOI to your dataset, making it permanently citable and ensuring long-term preservation.